

WONDERFUL DANIEL GLOBAL SCHOOL

KINGDOM LIFE CHRISTIAN UNIVERSITY,
SOUTH CAROLINA, USA

Managing Life from Within: A Self-Evaluation Guide

RECLAIMING CONTROL, CLARITY, AND CONFIDENCE THROUGH PERSONAL INSIGHT

Prepared by
Professor Ifeloju John
Executive Director

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This study is a guide to empower you on the management of your life, the journey, as you progress in the course of life. We provide **specialized knowledge for inclusivity and diversity for sustainability.**

...become **a global ambassador** in a **global community.**

THE LIFE MANAGEMENT

Introduction:

We have seen various aspects of management, be it business management, health management, administration, finance, environmental, conflict management, etc. However, we have seen various age groups of people that have failed woefully in their lifetime. Some have lots of regrets, sorrows, and “had I known” statements in their lives. *Had I known*, this is a common phrase used by people who have fallen victim to bad occurrences because they had no foreknowledge about life management. Life management, to some people, is the ability to take risks, as there are many factors to failure.

Life itself needs to be managed, and it is from this thought that the researcher has received a deep thought on the subject “the life management,” to include it in every one of our courses and curriculum at the institution. To teach our students, ministers, people, families, and community how to manage their lives.

This will be a program on personal development, personal management, and evaluation. However, it will also involve developing, and developing in what you do not know yet. Therefore, the studies of life management and life development will be taken based on an individual.

What you need to resolve as you grow in life and at each junction and season of your life, which the writer has classified as your Morning section, Afternoon section, and Night section. In this study, stages, sections, and seasons will be used interchangeably. And anything that needs fixing will be fixed in your life’s section of life.

Maneuver your way through in a godly and legal manner to achieve the best in every stage of your life. You may be in one stage, and life itself may not permit you to get to the other stage, and while you are thinking that you can’t make it to the next section of your life, if you think you won’t plan or achieve, life may also allow you to increase and get to the stage of your night. There are things you should possess in each stage of your life.

African World Case of Study (Image 1)

The Western World's Case of Study (Image 2)

The life strategy management you are to study is based in the African assumption of age but it may not necessarily be the same group of age in every nation of the world especially the western world.

STAGES OF LIFE

FUNDAMENTAL STAGE

What you need to possess in your morning if all things are equal.

Age 1-30years (Morning Stage)

- Education
- Good moral life
- Polite life
- Favourable background
- Course of life – Employment/work
- Good association
- BSc, BA, MSc, M.A, GCE, SSCE, FSLC, Birth Certificate BC.
- Marriage

BUILDING STAGE OR DEVELOPMENT STAGE

What you need to possess in your afternoon session if all things are equal.

Age 30-50years (Afternoon stage)

- Stability
- Establishment
- Fixing what has been missed in stage 1
- Marriage stability and having children
- Having a picture of your next generation
- Self-independence
- MA, MSc, PHD, Professorship, etc.
- Social and political recognition
- Ownership of lands and houses
- Foundation of legacy

FINISHING STAGE (OR BATON, LEGACY STAGE)

What you need to possess in your night session if all things are equal

Age 51years and above

- Quickly fix what you have missed in your afternoon
- Building apartments
- Having children and grand children
- PhDs, Professorship
- Stability in career
- Self sufficiency
- Self-independence
- Kingdom and establishment

In image 1, we can see that the age of your morning session is quite more than the afternoon. Therefore in your morning stage if you are in good parenting hands they would have set a proper planning for your life development in motion, thus it will be easy to fix things properly even without prayer.

The RESULTS – when you miss anything in the morning stage. E.g. in your morning age group, what you may likely suffer will be:

- Illiteracy
- Bad attitude
- Bad company
- No qualifications
- Being a vagabond
- Broken home
- No choice of employment
- Lack of sufficient funds for business
- No choice of lifestyle
- Sorrow
- Helplessness
- Suicide
- Robbery to meet up needs and wants
- Eloping for marriage
- Lack of submission
- Anger
- Bitterness
- Un-forgiveness
- Lack of joy
- Dis-order

The RESULTS – when you miss anything in the afternoon stage. E.g. in your afternoon age group, what you may likely suffer will be:

- Hatred of life
- No husband, wife, or child
- Unemployment and joblessness
- Smoking and drugs abuse
- Illegal acts
- Activists
- Un-cured pains
- Rudeness and disobedience to authorities
- Rebellion and assassinations

- Refection
- Instability
- Depending on people for livelihood. House rent, food, clothing, furniture, etc.
- Drinking for comfort
- Lack of care for children, wife, husband
- Un-forgiveness
- Lack of progress

The RESULTS – when you miss anything in the night stage. E.g. in your night age group, what you may likely suffer will be:

- Regret
- Sorrows
- Being a tenant
- Living a beggar's life
- Silent death
- Lack of food(hunger)
- Humiliations
- Rejection
- Hopelessness
- Burden on children
- Un-changed attitude
- Wickedness
- Joining cults, witchcraft and witches for survival and spiritual authority
- Waiting for help
- Having no choice.

The above phenomenon brings in a total fear into one's mind, especially when you have missed some steps in your life age group. Therefore, we need to re-adjust every aspect of our lives that we have ignored. We are to take new positive habits to rebuild our homes, marriages, and future for the betterment of tomorrow or the next stage (session of life).

We are to endure the present pressure to attain and regain what we have lost in any aspect of our life in order not to regret.

Individuals have to motivate themselves for greater performance. As you see in this course, especially the type of suffering and many negative effects that happen to anyone that misses the order of life.

The problems are on the rise because they are carried over from one age group to another age group; this brings more pressure in life, which could lead to different heart diseases and depression.

Therefore, it is more advisable to tackle the problems as quickly as possible:
Many years ago, the writer had an opportunity to study abroad with full scholarship at an American university based in Europe, but in an interview with the university administration's representative, the age of the writer was too high to be admitted to study MSc. The scholarship had to be given to a younger brother by the author.

Time is more than money. Time is life, therefore, life management is how you have to manage your time, stages of life, in the context of your life span right from the day you were born to the day you will exit this physical world. However, when you were born you didn't know, unless you are conscious about life and rational about your environment, your position in life and about the stage you are in life, you can do nothing.

Therefore, it can be deduced that from the on-set of your consciousness about life and you should start your life management and fix in what you've lost.

Comparisons and Contrasts

Key Note:

A – Where you are coming from (heaven or above)

B – Where you are on earth full of activities

C – Where you are going to after your activities or life on earth (the unseen world)

Spiritual Connotation

A – Unknown – Spiritual Beings: mystery (unexplainable)

B – Known – Life, life management, life development, activity of lives.

C – Unknown – Limited knowledge, Heaven or Hell.

You can only control and manage B because that is where your consciousness is at the moment.

The life in you now is for this planet earth, which is why we are treating the subject of how to manage the life you are having now. So as to be productive without any regret and if there is one, how do you manage it.

Life is Always in Motion(You are Heading Somewhere)

The above are the Life matrixes in life management which you must study personally and learn your lessons as quickly as possible.

Sometimes in life, you see opportunities coming your ways, that of employments, marketing, buying of lands, finance, marriage, child bearing, travelling abroad, friendship and profitable relationships, getting material possession and favour from a master or the opposite sex etc. Your response to these will bring about the leverage of your life management and progressive growth in life and other aspect of life.

However, if you have failed to take up the risk involved and you have failed to maximize or use fully what life have brought to you to the best of your advantage it will come to a stage or session of your life that you may not see such development band opportunities, it may be scanty or in scarcity depending on your discipline and endeavors.

But Life is in motion, up and down as a rotation globe, such opportunity that you have once missed may appear again and again or one more, in the journey of life.

Please, be sensitive enough to utilize it for your recovery and restoration of what you have missed.

In the Life Matrix in figure 4, what you see in your morning afternoon, may repeat itself in your morning night.

Sometimes, it could be in your afternoon, you see money overflowing in your purse, what you must do is to use it effectively for your permanent stability because, you can't predict the rolling of the globe, Like British weather, so as Life rotates and brings the favours to your side, Kindly be sensitive to dig your holes in the rock as the rain is falling, else you will waste some of the resources of Life.

THE SIX STEPS OF LIFE DEVELOPMENTS

- STEP 1: -Moral Foundations
Year [1-12] -Building Backgrounds
 -Building Reasoning
- STEP 2: -Building Right Moral Life
Year [13-19] -Academic Foundations
 -Having Right Backgrounds
 -Providing Right Environment
 -Providing Right Association
 -Career Foundation
- STEP 3: -Marital Foundation
Year [20-30] -Building Academic
 -Occupational Foundation
- STEP 4: -Economical Foundation
Year [31-40] -Building Occupations
 -Establishment
 -Building Marital Life
 -Raising Children
 -Building Name
 -House Foundation, Prosperity
- STEP 5: -Governmental Foundation
Year [41-50] -Kingdom, Domain
 -Building House
 -Economic
 -Political and Social
 -Establishment and Stability
- STEP 6: -Legacy
Year [51 above] -Building Governmentally
 -Seeing your Next Generation
 -Dominion, kingdom and Life Reigning

Who is Responsible to Manage Your Life for You?

Your parents are responsible to manage your life for you at a certain age; say 1–17 years, after which they are not responsible for anything you undertake. Although it varies from one country to another to some countries, it is age 1–14 years, some nations are from 1–16 years, while others are 18 years. Especially in developing countries, parenting manages the life of their children till after marriage, while in the Western world, they believe their children should take their lives into their hands as early as possible so as to be responsible for their lives and face every consequence of every decision that was taken by the children.

However, what about the child whose mother and father died in a motor accident ,who is responsible to manage the life of such a child? Government or what? The extended family or whom? These are issues why you can't hold anyone responsible for your failure.

Individuals are responsible for their life.

Therefore, you are responsible for your life, be it success or failure. God the Creator has created us in a way that you will see some people that have no opportunity that you have, and they have made it in life.

You are responsible for your marriage, finance, house, business, health,unless you were born with some kind of ailment, future, childbearing, etc.

Life Development

You need to strategize yourself and grow in these areas of Life, have a quick insight and take a step of action, be it by faith or somehow but let it be Legal. Just keep yourself developing and as such you will have nothing that is left undone, and untouched in Life.

- Marriage
- Child bearing
- Home
- Investment, business
- Trade, training and schooling
- Employment / Job
- Plan Retirement before you are retired by your boss or government.
- Take an insurance life policy and retirement policy
- Building yourself
- Building your career
- Building your home (either in a rural/urban area)

